

The Dunhuang Platform Sūtra

also known as “The Platform Sūtra”

By Morten Schlütter, University of Iowa

Entry tags: Chan Buddhism (chan zong 禪宗), Religious Group, Text, Chinese Buddhist text, Chan Buddhist text, Early Chan text, Chinese Religion, Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Literary Chinese, Language, Classical-Middle-Modern Sinitic, Sino-Tibetan, Sinitic

This entry is about the version of the Platform Sūtra that was found at the Mogao caves in Dunhuang, China, in year 1900. The full title of the text is The Sūtra of the Perfection of Wisdom of the Supreme Vehicle of the Sudden Teaching of the Southern Tradition: "The Platform Sūtra Preached by the Great Master Huineng, the Sixth Patriarch, at the Dafan Monastery in Shaozhou, in one fascicle, including the bestowal of the formless precepts; recorded and compiled by the disciple Fahai, Spreader of the Dharma" (南宗頓教最上乘摩訶般若波羅蜜經六祖惠能大師於韶州大梵寺施法壇經一卷 兼受無相戒弘法弟子法海集記). Three complete copies of the text were found at Dunhuang in addition to several fragments. The text is thought to have been composed ca. 780.

Date Range: 780 CE - 1000 CE

Region: East Asia [780-1279 CE]

Region tags: East Asia

Area in which the Platform Sūtra may have been known by the mid-ninth century.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Yampolsky, Philip B., trans. *The Platform Sutra of the Sixth Patriarch* (Translations from the Asian Classics). New York: Columbia University Press, 2012.
- Source 2: Red Pine (Porter, Bill), trans. *The Platform Sutra: The Zen Teaching of Hui-neng*, Counterpoint, 2008.

Notes: Both translations include analysis and translation of the Dunhuang Platform Sutra, including the Chinese text (although based on two slightly different versions of the Dunhuang text)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://terebess.hu/zen/huineng-eng.html>
- Source 1 Description: Links to a number of sources on the Platform Sutra and Huineng

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.ss.ncu.edu.tw/~calin/altar.html>

– Source 1 Description: Facsimiles of most major editions of the Platform Sūtra in pdf format. The Dunhuang texts are marked "a."

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: Three copies of the text from the Dunhuang manuscript cache are extant, all written with brush on paper in a booklet format.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 780 CE - 1279 CE

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 780 CE - 1279 CE

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: Handmade paper

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The extant copies of the text from Dunhuang are written on paper of various qualities

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: It is assumed by scholars that the text went through a number of different modifications by members of different groups before it reached the form we know from the Dunhuang Platform Sutra.

Notes: Scholars have noticed different, sometimes conflicting, voices in the text.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: At the time the text was first circulated it was not considered canonical. However, later versions were included in the Chinese Buddhist canon.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The text is written in a semi-colloquial language, not common for Buddhist texts in this period.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: However, the Dunhuang Platform Sutra, the earliest version of the text, is clearly meant to convince readers about Huineng's status as the Sixth Patriarch of Chan, as opposed to his "rival" Shenxiu (606?-706) who by some at the time was considered the Sixth Patriarch

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: The Dunhuang Platform Sutra pushes a claim, at the time not broadly accepted, about a special lineage of direct enlightenment traced back to the historical Buddha through the Indian Bodhidharma who travelled to China, and that Huineng is the sixth patriarch and only legitimate heir to this lineage.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Notes in the extant manuscripts of the Dunhuang Platform Sutra indicate audience responses in a ritual of bestowing "formless precepts" and it is quite possible the text was used as a kind of ritual manual at some point in its early history.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

Notes: It is stated several times in the text that copies of the Platform Sutra should be transmitted to followers of Huineng as proof of their authority to teach (with attached reference to the place, the date, and the name of the person receiving the text), but given only to those with superior wisdom and virtue. It seems implied that such people would be monastic teachers.

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This seems very unlikely

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There may have been some esoteric function to a copy of the text in the possession of a Buddhist master

- ↳ Does the text serve a protective function?
– No
- ↳ Does the text serve a healing function?
– No
- ↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?
– No
- ↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?
– No
- ↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?
– No
- ↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?
– No
- ↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?
– No
- ↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?
– No
- ↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?
Please specify the substances in the sub-questions
– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: Three complete copies of the Dunhuang Platform Sutra was found among the texts in the "Library Cave" that was discovered in year 1900 at the Mogao Caves in Dunhuang, but they are virtually identical. (Later, other versions of the text appeared, but this entry only addresses the Dunhuang version of the text).

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text can be seen as a response to earlier Chan texts with competing claims.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– No

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Part of a body of Chan/Zen literature

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The bestowal of the Formless Precepts in the text may constitute a form of ritual manual

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Notes: The text describes a series of one-per-generation "patriarchs," beginning with the Seven buddhas of the past to the historical Buddha, and eventually through Bodhidharma ending with Huineng as the sixth patriarch in China.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Implied (a given in Buddhist thought)

↳ In human form?

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form?

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– No

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: There is a reference to the interment of Huineng coffin, but no details are given.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: References to Buddhas and Bodhisattvas

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: The text implies the standard Buddhist view that there are many Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, while at the same time indicating the such beings are reflected in the human enlightened mind.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– No

Notes: Buddhas and Bodhisattvas are presented as equally powerful

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: Selflessness in the sense that there is no self.

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: In the sense of loyalty to Huineng and his teaching

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
Notes: To Huineng and his teaching

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes
Notes: In a number of places the text states that followers should avoid argumentation/disputation (諍).

↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Notes: The text states that it should not be taught to those of inferior wisdom, who would not understand, and could even be harmed by it.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The text contains a ritual of the bestowal of a set of "formless precepts," that likely was performed by those who had received the test in transmission.

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

Notes: An "autobiography" presented by Huineng describes the dramatic events surrounding his recognition as the Sixth Patriarch

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

Notes: There are some elements in the text that may have been understood as humorous.

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Notes: The story of Huineng presented in the text was no doubt meant to be entertaining.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: A group of people promoting Huineng as the Sixth Patriarch

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The text states that it must only be transmitted to those of superior wisdom, and so must at some point have been controlled by people who viewed themselves as heirs to Huining's teaching.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– A state

Notes: Emperor Daozong (1032-1101) of Liao had the Platform Sūtra burned as a spurious work, and it also seems to have been excluded from the Song (960-1279) Buddhist canon collections

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: Presumably the text would have been taught within the wall of monasteries, at least for a couple of generations after Huineng.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: In the text, Huineng directly addresses lay people in his audience and states that one does not have to be a monastic to practice his teachings,

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the text only may be transmitted to qualified individuals.

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: However, there are no female voices in the text.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Dunhuang Platform Sūtra, Schlütter, Morten, and Stephen F. Teiser. Readings of the Platform Sutra. Columbia University Press, 2012. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=fa3K4Q3viikC>.

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